

Banks Performance and Economic Growth: Evidence from West Africa

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Abstract:

This paper uses empirical econometric models to analyze Bank performance on GDP using panel data from 15 countries in West Africa. Data from 1996 to 2017 was used to make a statistical inference. Unit root test, cointegration test, fully modified ordinary least square (FMOLS) and Granger causality test were performed. A total of nine variables are employed in the study. GDP per capita, dependent variable which proxy's economic growth, return on assets and return on equity as independent variables. Government effectiveness, corruption control, interest rate and inflation as control variables. It was discovered that there is stationarity at first difference and that long run relationship exists among the dependent and independent variables. The fully modified OLS results showed that all the independent variables and the control variables have 1% significant relationship with the dependent variable. The regulatory bodies of the various countries in the sub-region are to ensure efficient management of Banks to avoid the situation of institutional failure which is a major issue in most developing countries. Stringent measures must equally be put in place to fight corruption.

Keywords: Bank performance, economic growth, financial sector, West Africa

1. Introduction

The health of a country's economy to a larger extent depends on the soundness of the banking sector. Instability in the banking sector and other financial intermediaries in any country can bring the whole economy to a standstill. The strength of most businesses depends on the ability of banks to provide them the needed facilities to undertake major deals. Persistent increase profitability and solid solvency are some major indications of good banking performance. Safeguarding the stability of the financial system and minimizing the risks of negative spillovers from the banking sector to the rest of the economy is the key objective of banking supervision as there is enough evidence to show that banks can not only promote growth but also endanger it, Svetlana and Olga (2017). It is, however, important to note that the magnitude of role played by banks depends on the long term economic dynamics of the country (Nasir, Ali & Khokar, 2014; Levine, 1998; 1999).

There has been a lot of happenings in the banking industry in the West African region in recent times. Within a period of two years, sixteen indigenous Ghanaian Banks collapsed as the main regulatory body-thus Bank of Ghana embarked on reforms to make the banking sector robust. Two major reasons for the collapse of most of these banks were poor cooperate with governance and inability to meet the new Bank of Ghana minimum capital requirement. The collapse of indigenous banks has become a set back to the effort of promoting indigenous Ghanaians to take control of the economy by building strong local institutions (Jerry, 2018). Four banks in Nigeria were fined N5.65bn in total by the Central Bank of Nigeria for illegally facilitating the transfer abroad of \$8.134bn for MTN, a South African telecom firm (Rafiq Raji, 2018). The very institutions that are supposed to be facilitating economic growth and progress were stifling it. It is an undisputable fact that countries that have strong and stable monetary and financial systems tend to build up their economic development much more rapidly (Ayman 2017)

With the intended implementation of a single currency in the sub-region, which will be controlled by the West African Monetary Agency (WAMA), West Africa Monetary Institute (WAMI) and the Central Bank of the various countries. This will go a long way to boost economic growth though it can equally plunge the whole region into a financial crisis if care is not taken.

Banks in the West African sub-region continue to struggle due to poor macroeconomic conditions and over-dependency of economies on the export of raw materials. The interrelationship between bank performance and

economic growth in the sub-region is a topic of much importance for both bank supervisors as well as macroeconomic policymakers in general.

To reduce vulnerability to external shocks threatened by the dependence of several economies, especially Nigeria (the biggest economy in the region), on oil or other mineral extraction, West African countries must increase domestic input into their products through manufacturing, especially processing minerals and agricultural products (African Development Bank, 2018)

The impact of Bank performance and the financial sector as a whole on economic development has always been an issue of debate among economists and academics. McKinnon (1973) argued that country with a patchy financial system where individuals have to rely on their own savings for investment that country will not be able to rally funds to shift to more productive technologies and hence development prospects would suffer. However, Lucas (1988) has a different opinion. He argued that the development of financial institutions had been overstressed as a factor for economic development.

Svetlana and Olga (2017) evaluated the links between banks and GDP growth in Latvia using Granger causality and Johansen cointegration tests based on quarterly data from 2001 to 2015. They reviewed several indicators for banking development to establish their relevance for GDP growth:

Ale (2016) undertook a study to find the influence of the banking industry on the growth of the economy using the Multilayer Perception to define functions of Universal Bank, Cooperative Bank, and Thrift Bank as predictors of Gross Domestic Product growth. Series from 2003- 2013 were used. It was found that Universal banks have been growing tremendously, taking huge shares of growth compared to the other two bank types. Meantime, the Gross Domestic Product was found to be steadily growing over the same period with a significant spike in 2004. His findings corroborated with Mohammed Ziaur Rhman et al. (2015) who posited that combined causality existed among the variables used in their study

Ahmad and Malik (2009) examined the effects of financial sector development on economic growth. Using GMM with data from 35 developing countries over the period of 1970-2003. They concluded that financial sector development affects per capita GDP hence economic growth.

Specifically, this paper is motivated by the zeal to contribute to existing knowledge and fills up a gap in the econometric-based empirical literature on the performance of Banks in west Africa on Economic growth. While a lot of econometric studies have been done on the impact of Bank performance and profitability and other related areas, little work has been done when it comes to Economic growth covering all west African countries. The study intends to investigate the relationship between variables that are included directly in the efficiency and performance of the banking sector and contribute to the economic growth of countries in the West African sub-region.

The study is divided into four-folds; section 1 introduces the study and reviews existing literature, section 2 describes the data and methodology for the study, section 3 reports the finding results and discussion and section 4 concludes the study.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Data

The study used panel data from 15 West African countries from the period 1996 to 2017. The study's objective is to assess the impact that banks in West Africa have on their economic growth hence it uses country level data from World Bank's World Development Indicator, World Governance Indicators and Global financial development database. The dependent variable for the study is economic growth and it is measured by proxy of gross domestic product per capita. However, the independent variables that study employed are a return on assets and return of equity. In order to firmly ascertain the impact of banks' performance, the study considered the two variables as proxies to measure banks' performance due to the bias that only one of the variables can put out. To control for macroeconomic consequences, the study has considered some macroeconomic factors and

other external factors as well as to control for economic growth. The control variables used for the study are corruption control, inflation, interest rate, regulation quality and unemployment.

2.2 Model specification

The econometric model that the study has considered can be written as:

$$\text{Economic growth} = f(\text{Banks performance} + \text{control variables}) \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), Economic growth is measured by proxy of gross domestic product per capita; banks' performance is measured by proxies of return on assets and return on equity, control variables are corruption control, inflation, interest rate, unemployment rate, regulatory quality and government effectiveness. Some of the variables were transformed into their natural logarithm to avoid fluctuation in the data series thus all the variables except the regulatory quality and government effectiveness. After taking the natural logarithm of the variables then the econometric model transformed into equation (2) below;

$$\ln gdppc_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln roa_{it} + \beta_2 \ln corrup_{it} + \beta_3 \ln goveff_{it} + \beta_4 \ln inf_{it} + \beta_5 \ln int_{it} + \beta_6 \ln unemp_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$\ln gdppc_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln roe_{it} + \beta_2 \ln corrup_{it} + \beta_3 \ln goveff_{it} + \beta_4 \ln inf_{it} + \beta_5 \ln int_{it} + \beta_6 \ln unemp_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

In the equations (2) and (3), β_0 represents the intercept of regression, ε is the error term or stochastic error or disturbances which the independent variables could not represent; i represents the cross-section of the countries and t represents the time period of 1996 to 2017.

2.3 Methodology

The study employed panel data methodologies to run its analysis to make a statistical inference. The methodologies used for the study are; panel unit root tests, cointegration test, fully modified ordinary least square (FMOLS) and granger causality tests.

The first step of the study is to compute for the summary statistics to find the mean, median and standard deviation of the variables. Moreover, to also do Skewness, Kurtosis and Jarque-Bera test to find the sequence of the distribution. Subsequently, panel unit root test is performed to ascertain stationarity among the variables. However, the purpose of the unit root tests is to reject the null hypothesis, which posits that there is unit root in the variables hence further extension of the regression model to analyse the data will make the regression process spurious. The following unit root tests are used; Levin et al. (2002) LLC test, Im-Pesaran & Shim test IPS (Im et al., 2003) and ADF-Fisher and PP-Fisher tests (Maddala & Wu, 1999). After it has been ascertained there is no evidence of unit root in the variables then the study tests for cointegration to establish the long run relationship that exists among the variables thus the dependent and independent variables.

Furthermore, the regression analysis then becomes the next step; the main regression method for the study is the fully modified ordinary least square (FMOLS) for its statistical inference. Finally, the study then performs granger causality test to ascertain the direction of causality among the dependent and independent variables. The expected direction is either unidirectional or bidirectional and also the null hypothesis posits that none of the variables granger causes another. Therefore, the test of granger causality will either validate the null hypothesis or reject it.

3. Empirical results and findings discussion

3.1 Summary statistics

Table 1 reports the summary statistics of the variables and it can be reported that the average rate of corruption control in West Africa was -0.54 annually, average rate of economic growth was 6.58% annually and the

average growth in banks performance was 0.28% as in return on equity and 2.26% as in return on assets. Details of the statistics can be found in table 1. However, the Jarque-Bera test confirms that data is not in normal distribution hence it is leptokurtic as the Kurtosis test reports.

Table 1 Summary Statistics

	corrup	lngdppc	lninf	lnint	lnroe	lnunemp	regqty	lnroa	goveff
Mean	-0.540	6.581	4.264	1.573	0.284	1.367	-0.540	2.263	-0.684
Median	-0.641	6.439	4.463	1.687	0.324	1.454	-0.479	2.680	-0.682
Maximum	1.143	8.171	5.331	2.925	2.259	2.511	0.128	4.837	0.366
Minimum	-1.702	4.811	0.000	-1.114	-3.927	-1.255	-2.024	-1.538	-1.885
Std. Dev.	0.537	0.621	0.900	0.764	0.805	0.748	0.437	1.253	0.516
Skewness	0.649	0.662	-3.621	-0.855	-1.138	-1.067	-0.562	-0.875	0.056
Kurtosis	3.293	3.008	17.178	3.273	7.505	4.561	2.774	2.686	1.903
Jarque-Bera	24.381	24.072	3484.863	41.204	350.219	96.140	18.083	43.446	16.732
Probability	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Observations	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330	330

3.2 Panel unit root tests

The study conducted panel unit root tests to ensure stationarity among the variables to avoid spurious regression and the results of the tests can found in table 2. From table2, it can be established that four tests were used to test for stationarity. Again, at level form there was evidence of stationarity in all the variables except that corrup was not stationary with LLC and ADF-Fisher tests, goveff was not stationary with LLC test and lngdppc was not stationary with LLC and IPS tests but at first difference, all the variables became stationary hence the study can conclude that at first difference there is an evidence of stationarity in the variables. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is unit root in the variables.

Table 2 Panel Unit root tests

	corrup	goveff	lngdppc	lnif	lnint	lnroe	lnunemp	regqty	lnroa
LEVEL									
LLC	0.291	1.186	-1.098	-5.814***	-2.441***	-7.001***	-0.854*	-0.696***	-7.476***
IPS	-1.645**	-1.571**	0.923	-1.313*	-2.283***	-7.123***	0.300*	-3.438***	-6.823***
ADF-Fisher	37.687	40.470*	49.201***	41.183*	58.127***	120.725***	28.722**	59.6811***	113.988***
PP-Fisher	172.041***	190.131***	45.829***	48.601***	60.387***	376.187***	10.59*	149.184***	124.547***
FIRST DIFFERENCE									
LLC	-57.615	-71.630***	-7.615***	-10.694***	-20.317***	-17.078***	-8.262***	-50.647***	-16.995***
IPS	-53.480***	-61.904***	-9.917***	-8.447***	-20.000***	-18.399***	-7.374***	-44.420***	-17.314***
ADF-Fisher	2514.35***	2456.07***	149.472***	146.076***	301.429***	279.890***	108.258***	1563.32***	262.887***
PP-Fisher	2582.92***	2449.03***	182.808***	197.594***	426.152***	1229.76***	97.632***	1568.52***	1173.28***

Note: *** connotes 1% significance level, ** connotes 5% significance level, * connotes 10% significance level

3.3 Panel cointegration test

The study performed a cointegration test to find evidence of long run relationship that exists between the independent and dependent variables. The results of the test can be found in table 3 and it reports that at none to at most 3 with trace test there was no evidence that the variables are cointegrated. Also, at none to at most 1 with Max-eigen test there was no evidence of cointegration, but from at most 4 to at most 7 with trace test and at most 2 to at most 7, there was evidence of cointegration or long run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration among the variables is rejected.

Table 3 Cointegration test

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Fisher Stat.* (from trace test)			Fisher Stat.* (from max-eigen test)		
	Prob.	Sig.		Prob.	Sig.	
None	20.790	0.894		20.790	0.894	
At most 1	20.790	0.894		20.790	0.894	
At most 2	16.640	0.977		71.900	0.000	***
At most 3	1.386	1.000		259.300	0.000	***
At most 4	276.300	0.000	***	276.300	0.000	***
At most 5	321.400	0.000	***	240.100	0.000	***
At most 6	160.500	0.000	***	114.900	0.000	***
At most 7	107.800	0.000	***	107.800	0.000	***

Note: *** connotes 1% significance level

3.4 Results of regression analysis (Fully modified OLS)

Table 4 displays the regression analysis results by using a fully modified ordinary least square (FMOLS). From the table, the results can be interpreted as robust or strong results because, from all indications, all the independent variables (Lnroa) and (Lnroe) and the control variables showed 1% significant relationship with the dependent variable (Ingddpc). Banks' return on assets showed a positive and statistically significant relationship with economic growth with coefficient of 0.0123, confirming that a percentage increase in banks' return on assets will lead to 0.012% increase in economic growth. With regards to return on equity, it showed a negative and statistically significant relationship with economic growth with coefficient of -0.008. In the other words, a percentage increase in the return on equity of banks will lead to 0.008 decreases in economic growth. Taking into account the control variables, corruption control, inflation, unemployment rate and regulatory quality showed positive and statistically significant relationship with economic growth at coefficient of 0.161, 0.102, 0.038 and 0.148, respectively. These coefficients signal that a percentage increase in corruption control, inflation, unemployment and regulatory quality will lead to 0.161%, 0.102%, 0.038% and 0.148% increase, respectively. However, interest rate and government effectiveness showed a negative and statistically significant relationship with economic growth with coefficients of -0.046 and -0.233 respectively. The negative relationships confirm that a percentage increase in interest rate and government effectiveness will lead to 0.046% and 0.233% decrease in economic growth respectively.

Table 4 Results of analysis with FMOLS

	coefficient	T-statistic	coefficient	T-statistic
Corrupt	0.161	7.894***	0.178	9.030***
Goveff	-0.233	-11.223***	-0.236	-11.594***
Lnif	0.102	23.447***	0.100	23.348***
Lnint	-0.046	-7.416***	-0.0345	-6.272***
Lnunemp	0.038	3.994***	0.0378	4.045***
Regqty	0.148	7.277***	0.126	6.385***
Lnroa	0.0123	3.677***		
Lnroe			-0.008	(-1.857)*

Note: *** connote 1% significance level, * connote 10% significance level

3.5 Granger causality test

In table 5, the results of the granger causality are reported. From the table, it can be ascertained that there is an evidence of granger causality; hence, the null hypothesis that there is no granger causality is rejected. The results exhibit an evidence of bidirectional causality from return on assets to return on equity, return on assets to interest rate and regulatory quality to inflation; the bidirectional granger causality confirms that a change in any of the variables granger causes the other vice versa. However, there is also an evidence of unidirectional granger causality stemming from inflation to corruption control, corruption control to interest rate, return on equity to corruption control, unemployment rate to corruption control, corruption control to regulatory quality, regulatory quality to economic growth, inflation to interest rate, return on equity to interest rate, return on assets to interest rate and return on equity to regulatory quality.

Table 5 Granger causality test

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	
LNINFLATION does not Granger Cause CORRUPTION	300	2.384	0.094	*
CORRUPTION does not Granger Cause LNINTRATE	300	2.348	0.097	*
LNROE does not Granger Cause CORRUPTION	300	4.302	0.014	**
LNUMEMPL does not Granger Cause CORRUPTION	300	4.187	0.016	**
CORRUPTION does not Granger Cause REGULATORY_Q	300	5.623	0.004	**
REGULATORY_Q does not Granger Cause LNGDPPC	300	5.656	0.004	**
LNINFLATION does not Granger Cause LNINTRATE	300	2.937	0.055	**
REGULATORY_Q does not Granger Cause LNINFLATION	300	2.800	0.062	*
LNINFLATION does not Granger Cause REGULATORY_Q	300	3.671	0.027	**
LNROE does not Granger Cause LNINTRATE	300	2.436	0.089	*
ROA does not Granger Cause LNINTRATE	300	6.126	0.003	**
LNINTRATE does not Granger Cause ROA	300	4.533	0.012	**
LNROE does not Granger Cause REGULATORY_Q	300	2.964	0.053	**
ROA does not Granger Cause LNROE	300	2.400	0.093	*
LNROE does not Granger Cause ROA	300	2.488	0.085	*

Note: ** connote 5% significance level, * connote 10% significance level

4. Conclusion

The objective of the study was to assess the impact of banks' performance on economic growth in West Africa hence the use of panel data of 15 West African countries from 1996 to 2017. The study used panel data methodologies such panel unit root tests, co-integration tests, fully modified ordinary least square and granger causality tests.

The study finds that banks' performance has positive and statistically significant relationship with economic growth when return on assets is used as proxy measure of banks' performance, but when return on equity is used as proxy measure of banks' performance then the relationship is negative and statistically significant. Moreover, there are positive and statistically significant relationships that exist between inflation, unemployment, regulatory quality, corruption control and economic growth. Consequently, interest rate and government effectiveness also showed negative and statistically significant relationship with economic growth.

Since there is a positive statistically significance between economic growth and bank performance, the regulatory bodies of the various countries in the sub-region are to ensure efficient management of Banks to avoid the situation of institutional failure, which is a major issue in most developing countries.

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